

SIMPLE ADVERBS IN KARAKALPAK: ETYMOLOGY AND MORPHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE

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Abstract. The paper investigates two main categories of simple adverbs in Karakalpak: root adverbs and historically derived adverbs. Examining the etymological origins and usage of these adverbs, the article highlights the debate surrounding their classification. This analysis emphasizes the importance of recognizing both absolutely root and historically derived adverbs in understanding the complexity of Karakalpak.

Keywords: Karakalpak, adverb, etymology, Turkic languages, morphology.

This study explores simple adverbs in the Karakalpak language. Many of these adverbs have a rich history, dating back to ancient Turkic languages. The paper highlights the distinction between absolutely root and historically derived adverbs. It also examines the etymology and usage of these adverbs. The article also explores how scholars have approached the classification of these adverbs, highlighting the debate surrounding their origins.

Krushevsky notes that “a significant part of adverbs in fusional languages are frozen word forms of nouns, adjectives, and verbs, that is to say, they are secondary formations in their genesis since they were formed mainly from fragments of notional words [4, 124]. Kozlova, in her work “Comparative typology of English and Russian languages”, states that this is the history of the origin of such English adverbs as, for example, “*since, home, always, today*”, such German adverbs as “*abends*” ‘in the evening’, or such Russian adverbs as “*неуком*” (on foot), “*бегом*” (running), *вприпрыжку* (skipping), “*втихомолку*” (quietly), “*шепотом*” (whispering), etc. [4, 124]. Such adverbs occur in Karakalpak. As a rule, simple adverbs in the Karakalpak language include the oldest adverbs, which are almost unchanged in the ancient Turkic written monuments. They are also included in the active vocabulary of the Karakalpak language. Many of them are the result of ancient word production. However, at the synchronous level, these words are not divided into a root and a suffix, so they are considered non-derived. Such phenomena are considered in the work of Shukurov “Prototypical adverbs in the Azerbaijani language”. The author notes that these “adverbs, which are indecomposable from the point of view of modern linguistics, are historically derived” [11, 137-145]. According to Iskhakov and Palmbakh, prototypical adverbs do not decompose into their component parts from the point of view of the modern language and are used in a certain frozen form. Nevertheless, they are historically derived from a particular word [3, 417]. Thus, the prototypical adverbs are those that are not divided into separate morphemes at the

synchronous level, but which are historically derived. Below we will consider such simple adverbs, which are diachronically derived.

Many simple adverbs of the Karakalpak language are found in early monuments and dictionaries. Accordingly, in the dictionary of Mahmud al-Kashgari in the XI century, many units were recorded, which are now widely used in speech. For example, the word *biltir* 'last year' was first encountered as *buldur* 'last year' in the work of Mahmud al-Kashgari in the XI century [10, 71]. Thereby, the adverb *biltir* is widely used in the Karakalpak language: *Biltir maldi dápterge alip edi* [6, 71]. 'Last year, the cattle were taken to the inventory'. The words *biyil* 'this year' and *búgin* 'today' are also considered as compound adverbs in some works devoted to the study of the Turkic languages [2, 23]. However, in the Karakalpak language, they are now considered simple adverbs formed in a lexical way [1, 220]. Likewise, Eshbaev refers to these words as simple adverbs and explains that they were initially compound; as a result of phonetic merging, they became a single word to an inconspicuous extent that they currently have absolute adverbial features. Besides, he believes that it is correct to say that etymologically they are compound adverbs that were syntactically formed from two words. He explains as follows: *biltir* was formed from *bir* 'one' and *jil* 'year', *biyil* was formed from *bul* 'this' and *jil* 'year', *búgin* was formed from *bul* 'this' and *kún* 'day' [2, 40-41]. Khudaibergenov, in his work "Morphology of Karakalpak Language", shows that the pronoun *bul* 'this' and the noun *kún* 'day' became one-word *búgin* 'today'. While their merging, historically morphophoneme /l-Ø/ and phonetically morphophoneme /k-g/ occur. He also shows that the word *biyil* 'this year' are formed from the words *bul* 'this' and *jil* 'year'. Historically morphophoneme /k-g/ occurs in the process of their merging [7, 108].

In the Karakalpak language, the word *kóp* 'a lot, much' is also used as an adverb: — *Shayıq, kóp sóley bermeńiz sharshap qalasız, — dedi Alif Qarabay bahadır* [5, 217]. "Sheikh, don't talk too much, you will get tired," Alif said'. This word is common in Turkic languages: *köp* in ancient Turkic, *кәп* in Kazakh, *кәп* in Kyrgyz. Sevortyan notes that he agrees with Bang's assumption according to which the word *kóp* originally meant 'a bloat, a heap' and then 'a lot'. Sevortyan also remarks that the word is correlative to the verb base *kóp* 'increase, grow, multiply' and shows as an example the Old Turkic verb *ük-* 'to collect, to accumulate, to amass' from which the words such as *ükil* 'much, a lot', *üküs* 'a lot', *ükün* 'whole lot, heap, crowd' are derived [8, 108].

The word *kesh* 'late' is found in the monuments of the old Uighur script: *ür keč boldy* 'a lot of time has passed'; in the work of Mahmud al-Kashgari: *keč* 'late (as an adjective)' [10, 82]. According to Bang, the basis of *keč* can be related to the verb *keč* 'to pass' [9, 51]. The simple adverb *kesh* 'late' is common Turkic, it is represented in many modern Turkic languages: in Turkish: *geç*, in Azerbaijani: *gec*; in Kazakh: *кеч*; in Uzbek: *kech*. In the Karakalpak language *kesh* is also used in the meaning 'late': *Ólim erte me, kesh pe, áytewir bir keledi* [5, 95]. 'Sooner or later, death will come one day'. In the form of *ge:če* appears in the temporal meaning in the work of Mahmud al-Kashgari: *geče* 'night'; in the Kutadgu Bilig: *keče jatty* 'I went to bed late at night' [10, 82]. In Karakalpak, the word *kesh* occur with meaning 'evening': *Keshte úyine baratırp, bosqa oynap júrgen balalardı kórse, "erten ustaxanağa kelińler, oris balasnan is úyrenińler" dep ketedi* [5, 303]. 'Returning home in the evening, if he sees that the children are playing in vain, he says: "Come to the forge tomorrow, learn from the Russian guy"'. However,

the word *keshe* is used with the meaning 'yesterday' in Karakalpak: *Keshe qawın urlıqqa barǵanbız...* [5, 205]. 'Yesterday we went to steal melons'.

One of the simple adverbs is *tez* 'quickly', which occurs in several Turkic languages. Nevertheless, the etymology is not yet known. In general, it is a unit of Karakalpak and other Turkic languages: in Uzbek: *tez*; in Kazakh: *mez*; in Azerbaijani: *tez*; in Karachay-Balkar: *mez*; in Tatar: *muз*; Crimean Tatar: *mez*. The present form seems to be Proto-Turkic. For example: - *Tez jeteyik biz, - deyip...* [6, 117]. '- Saying - let's get there soon...'. *Tımsallawǵa bul jas biy qálegen gáp astarın tez uǵadı* [5, 84]. When giving an example, this young 'biy' will quickly grasp any hint.

The analysis reveals that in the Karakalpak language, simple adverbs, many of which are the result of old word-formation, but at the synchronous level, non-derived adverbs. In other words, they are not divided into a root and affixes. However, there are definitely root adverbs. Thus, we can divide simple adverbs into two groups. The first group contains absolutely root adverbs: *tez* 'quickly', *kóp* 'a lot, much', *kesh* 'late'. The second group includes adverbs that historically represent derived words, but are morphologically non-derived at the synchronous level: *búgin* 'today', *bıltır* 'last year', *biyil* 'this year'.

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